

Research Software Workshop

Guidelines and metrics
for metadata curation

Housekeeping

 [Live note](#) taking document

<https://tinyurl.com/2023-03-24-RDA-RS-workshop>

[RDA Code of Conduct](#)

Organizing committee:

Committee (**FAIR-IMPACT/FC4E/RDA SSC IG**):

- Chair: Morane Gruenpeter (Inria/Software Heritage)
- Neil Chue Hong (SSI/EPCC)
- Sabrina Granger (Inria/Software Heritage)
- Elena Breitmoser (EPCC, University of Edinburgh)
- Mike Priddy (DANS)
- Mario Antonioletti (SSI/EPCC)
- Paula Martinez (ARDC/ReSA)
- Tom Honeyman (ARDC)
- Julia A Collins (CU/CIRES National Snow and Ice Data)
- Rita Meneses (Trust IT)

Slack space: [join here](#)

- Be kind. Be understanding. Be inclusive.
- Please **do Tweet** otherwise using the hashtag [#RS_workshop_RDAP20!](#)
- the workshop will be recorded
- Turn on your video if you don't mind sharing your face (or off if you do!)
- Please be aware that the session is being recorded and will be made publicly available
- Keep yourself muted
- General chat in the slack should be prioritized over the zoom chat.
- Do not aggressively speak over others or overly dominate the conversation in a group session, be inclusive of everyone.

Goals today

<https://tinyurl.com/2023-03-24-RDA-RS-workshop>

Have fun!

- Discover the metadata landscape
- Discover the FAIR4RS principles
- Collaborate with the larger research software community
- Provide valuable insight to the two FAIR-IMPACT deliverables:
 - D4.4 Guidelines for recommended metadata standard for research software within EOSC
 - D5.2 Metrics for automated FAIR software assessment in a disciplinary context

Agenda

<https://tinyurl.com/2023-03-24-RDA-RS-workshop>

9.00- 9.30	Introduction and overview of the workshop	
	An overview of the current landscape of metadata vocabularies and tools to support descriptive metadata curation (Morane Gruenpeter, Software Heritage)	
	An overview of FAIR4RS and existing tools to assess FAIRness of software (Neil Chue Hong, Software Sustainability Institute)	
	Outline the specific goals and objectives	
	Workshop activities explanation and questions	
9.45-10.45	Session A: Descriptive metadata - curation tools and workflows <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onsite: Morane Gruenpeter - Online: Paula Martinez 	Session B: Metrics for FAIR Research Software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onsite: Neil Chue Hong - Online: Mike Priddy
10.45-11.15	Coffee break	
11.15 -11.30	Report back from parallel session	
11.30 - 12.00	Plenary - Workshop conclusion	

Ice-breaker

<https://tinyurl.com/2023-03-24-RDA-RS-workshop>

Are you familiar with the following acronyms, publications or projects?

- [the SIRS report recommendations](#),
- the [FAIR4RS principles](#)
- FAIRCORE4EOSC
- FAIR-IMPACT
- the [CodeMeta initiative vocabulary](#)

Agenda

<https://tinyurl.com/2023-03-24-RDA-RS-workshop>

9.00- 9.30	Introduction and overview of the workshop	
	An overview of the current landscape of metadata vocabularies and tools to support descriptive metadata curation (Morane Gruenpeter, Software Heritage)	
	An overview of FAIR4RS and existing tools to assess FAIRness of software (Neil Chue Hong, Software Sustainability Institute)	
	Outline the specific goals and objectives	
	Workshop activities explanation and questions	
9.45-10.45	Session A: Descriptive metadata - curation tools and workflows <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onsite: Morane Gruenpeter - Online: Paula Martinez 	Session B: Metrics for FAIR Research Software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onsite: Neil Chue Hong - Online: Mike Piddy
10.45-11.15	Coffee break	
11.15 -11.30	Report back from parallel session	
11.30 - 12.00	Plenary - Workshop conclusion	

Agenda

<https://tinyurl.com/2023-03-24-RDA-RS-workshop>

9.00- 9.30	Introduction and overview of the workshop	
	An overview of the current landscape of metadata vocabularies and tools to support descriptive metadata curation (Morane Gruenpeter, Software Heritage)	
	An overview of FAIR4RS and existing tools to assess FAIRness of software (Neil Chue Hong, Software Sustainability Institute)	
	Outline the specific goals and objectives	
	Workshop activities explanation and questions	
9.45-10.45	Session A: Descriptive metadata - curation tools and workflows <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onsite: Morane Gruenpeter - Online: Paula Martinez 	Session B: Metrics for FAIR Research Software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onsite: Neil Chue Hong - Online: Mike Piddy
10.45-11.15	Coffee break	
11.15 -11.30	Report back from parallel session	
11.30 - 12.00	Plenary - Workshop conclusion	

Coffee break

<https://tinyurl.com/2023-03-24-RDA-RS-workshop>

Agenda

<https://tinyurl.com/2023-03-24-RDA-RS-workshop>

9.00- 9.30	Introduction and overview of the workshop	
	An overview of the current landscape of metadata vocabularies and tools to support descriptive metadata curation (Morane Gruenpeter, Software Heritage)	
	An overview of FAIR4RS and existing tools to assess FAIRness of software (Neil Chue Hong, Software Sustainability Institute)	
	Outline the specific goals and objectives of the workshop for the RDA community, including the aim to collect existing guidelines, identify gaps and extend interoperability	
	Share workshop participants profiles - on Roll call	
	Workshop activities explanation and questions	
9.45-10.45	Session A: Descriptive metadata - curation tools and workflows <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onsite: Morane Gruenpeter - Online: Paula Martinez 	Session B: Metrics for FAIR Research Software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Onsite: Neil Chue Hong - Online: Mike Piddy
10.45-11.15	Coffee break	
11.15 -11.30	Report back from parallel session	
11.30 - 12.00	Plenary - Workshop conclusion	

Workshop conclusion and next steps

- Q & A
- Identify synergies between guidelines and metrics
- Identify open issues, challenges and blockers from the session
- Next practical steps:
 - D4.4 deadline - June 2023
 - D5.2 deadline - September 2023
 - How to review and comment the deliverables?
 - Options:
 - Open document - only asynchronously
 - Webinar/online workshop (meeting + asynchronously comments)
 - Contribute to CodeMeta! (participate in the community discussion)
 - Discussion & votes until March 25th (if needed we can extend)

Thank you for contributing!

@fairimpact_eu /company/fair-impact-eu-project